

KHAZRATI PAKHLAVAN MAKHMUD MAUSOLEUM**Ismailov Tokhir Khushnubek ugli**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7735468>

Pahlavan Makhmud mausoleum¹ Shokhi Zinda in Samarkand², as Bahouddin Naqshband mausoleum in Bukhara³ the sacred shrine of the revered Uzbek, Turkmen, Karakalpak and other peoples is the most beautiful and luxurious among the architectural monuments of Khiva.

Pakhlan Makhmud (1247-1326) was a famous polwon, artisan Carpenter and great philosopher poet. The fame of this young man, who embodies physical and spiritual perfection, reaches from Movarounnahr and Khorasan to Iran and India. He goes to many cities of Khorazm, even India, where a fight with famous swans falls, but is not overcome anywhere, remaining the country's chief polo player all his life without his shoulder touching the ground. For this reason, a huge number of myths and legends appear among the people, which mention him as a famous polwon, a folk hero, a wonderful patriot and a poet. The people give him the nickname "Pakhlan" and venerate him as "Pahlavan Mahmud", "Polvon ota", "Hazrati Polvon pir". He took over from the heart of the khivans as the city's piri (chief patron), mausoleum - anchor of the city.

Concerning the construction of the city of Khiva, the son of Khiva Khudoyberdi Kushmukhammad ugli gave interesting facts in his 1831 work "Dili the wonder". He writes; - " in ancient times there were many cities with 4-5 gates of Khwarezm. One of them is Jurjonia, one is Urganch, another is Raml - (chagazor, gravel). The building of Muni was built by Som bin Nuh, made to resemble the ship that his father had repaired, and is equal to the template of the ship, and now they give Fame to Khivaq. This lafz is also said to be the Dead history of Saro, the governor of hazrat Pahlavan. Som come and hunt, sleep, dream, burn three hundred torches, take the surrounding soil to set the mark while the time is pleasant, put it on the sand and make it the template of the city. And on the sunset side of the castle, a kettle is dug out of the water. Some attribute Khivaq to Mun. The word of the harvest will break this fortress a lot and say that it is healed".

¹ https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pahlavan_Mahmud_majmuasi

² <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shohizinda>

³ https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bahouddin_Naqshband_majmuasi

In another retelling of the narrative, Som, son of the Prophet Noah, sleeps and dreams one day after a hunt, lying on top of a high hill in the sand. In the dream, his father enters and orders a castle to be built on the same sleeping land and says, "Build The Shape of the castle to look like my ship". When Som tells his father that "there will be a city in The Shape of a ship, and a swaying one like a ship," his father replies to him, "we'll drop an anchor in the middle of it." Som then builds a castle on the site, resembling the ship of his father Noah. That is, the one who drew and built the Tarh of the city was the son of Noah, Som.

The khivans consider the pahlavon Makhmud mausoleum to be an anchor thrown into the middle of the city by the Prophet Noah. That is why on the right wing of the large pedestal of the mausoleum there is an image of a ship on tin patterns. Until, as long as there is this mausoleum, the city of Khiva is at peace, so even the khivans keep it in sight, worship it. The entrance to the eastern side of the khanakah of the Tomb of Father polwon is the oldest monument in the entire complex and was led through a corridor starting from it to the Jome mosque.

The Chief Master of the mausoleum was the son of Odina Mukhammad of hazorasp, and Mukhammad Yusuf mehtar was the administrator of all the construction. The room under the dome, the burial chambers are covered with embossed tiles, the dome above it is made of gold. Tin tiles are square in shape and the pattern in one is not repeated in the same way as in the other. The lines of the pattern on them clearly connect with each other, and the overall decoration forms the plates decoration perfection not only knows, but also amazes a person with the skillful elaboration of their pattern and fluffy inside the room. "The mausoleum was given such an ornament that no one dared to give such a lush decoration after the time of Amir Temur," writes the art historian scholar I.I.Notkin⁴.

⁴ https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Iosif_Notkin

The

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mausoleum has attracted the attention of scientists from all XIX to the present time. Russian scientist who was in Khiva in 1873. L. Kostenko⁵ writes: "the most beautiful castle and therefore the holiest place is the polwon ota mosque in Khiva. This saint is venerated here as if he were Bahuddin in Bukhara. The golden dome above its dome is very beautiful".

The mausoleum was built by King Niyozkhan in the gatehouse "Bismillahirrahmanirrahim, La ilaha illallahu Mukhammad ur rasululloh" after passing through the door with the key, it goes out into the large courtyard. A well dug by King Niyozkhan in the middle of this courtyard, a summer mosque built by Mukhammad Rakhimkhan II on the east side, a qarikhana built by Isfandiorkhan on the west, with a large supa in front of it and a large Khanaqah with a pedestal facing South.

According to the Old Men of Khiva, when the father is old, Paklavon wills his disciples to bury him in the house where he sews and lives after his death. His disciples fulfilled his will and buried father Polwon in his house, later restoring the dome of the mausoleum of the chambermaid (nigirik) over the Tomb.

⁵ <https://www.prlib.ru/item/451354>

Gradually, graves begin to appear next to Father Polwon's grave, and they increase over the years to become a large cemetery. Three centuries later, when the city of Khiva became the center of the country, the rulers also begin to prepare a house of eternity for themselves from the side of Ota Polvon. Abulghazi Mukhammad Bahodirkhan, who died in 1663, is buried in Father Polwon's mausoleum. Under his son Anushakhan, a larger mausoleum will be built over the tombs of Pakhlavan Makhmud and Abulghazikhan. After that, the second half of the XVII century ruled Anushakhan⁶, Xudoydodkhan, Arang Khan, Jo'jikh Khan, Shohniyozkhan, Ruled at the beginning of the 18th century Yodgorkhan⁷, Temurg'ozikh Khan and their loved ones will be buried here.

In 1810 years Mukhammad Rakhimkhan I⁸ Palvon Ota's orders the mausoleum to be rebuilt and to make a place for himself from there. Mukhammad Yusuf mehtar, the administrator of this construction, knocks out outdated buildings and builds them from freshly baked bricks. A tomb is prepared for Mukhammad Rakhimkhan I in a large domed khonakah net. He is buried in this place upon Khan's death in 1825. Ollokulikhan, who succeeded his father on the throne, will build a corridor stretching from North to South, sticking to the eastern wall of the Great Dome of the mausoleum. In a deep ravine on the east side of the middle of the corridor, he prepares a tomb for himself and decrees the decoration of the entire mausoleum with tin.

Of Abdulla Boltaev⁹ writes, - "Mukhammad Yusuf mehtar brings to this work the son of Adina Mukhammad of hazorasp (a Chinese village), the son of Abdol Jabbar Ishaq of Khanqah (from Madir village), the son of Mullo Kadir Bardi of yangiariq (from Kattabog village), the son of Abdullah Ya'qub Husayn of Khiva (from Shaykhs village), the son of Mulla Mukhammad Panah (from Sangar village), the son of Mulla Nur Mukhammad and others". In order to clarify boltaev's statement, Bobojan Safarov wrote: "By Order of Mukhammad Rakhimkhan I, Mullah Abdul Karim (Mullah Uka would also say) of hazorasp made a master and completed it in 1225 (1810) Ah. The patterns of the dome of the mausoleum in Koshin were completed by 5 Masters in the entrepreneurship of Yusuf mehtar in 1254 (1238) Hijri.

The eastern wall patterns of the large dome were patterned by Mullah Nur Mukhammad of Khiva, the son of Mullah Abdul Jabbar Eshjan of Madras, and the

⁶ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Anushaxon>

⁷ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yodgorxon>

⁸ https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Muhammad_Rahimxon_I

⁹ <https://qomus.info/encyclopedia/cat-b/boltaev-uz/>

Western Wall by Mukhammad islimiy of Chinese Mullah Odina. The southern wall is patterned by the Sheikh Mullah Abdullakh jin Islomiy. The throne of the dome was made in eight layers by the great Mullah Almighty, who gave the islimi pattern, and also placed the tiles on the wall, leading the others. And those five who worked on the patterns of small domes as well". The work performed by these masters continues to amaze all scientists and tourists who come from the world to this day.

The pattern on the mausoleum tiles the color of the accent of the flowers was white, blue and rusty, and the choice of these colors was also not in vain. Because, from time immemorial, White was a symbol of purity, light, happiness and good luck, blue was a blue sky, protecting from a bad day and calming, symbolizing the rust - high faith and keeping from evil spirits. In patterns, too, universal meanings are hidden. For example, making a picture of various flowers into circular patterns, or the patterns themselves becoming circular, was done to dissuade an evil Intendant from his intention.

One of the coffins depicts a picture of a bird, which is a bulbul, symbolizing loyalty, that is, the loyalty of Ollokulikhan to his father and the Polvon to his father. That is why the coffins on the eights wall-taxia above the Quaternary wall of the large dome and even higher are inscribed with the ruboies of Pahlavon Makhmud. These ruboi of Ollokulikhan¹⁰ selected by order. The most luxurious palace in ollogulikhan Khiva - to Toshkhovli¹¹ before drying and decorating him with tiles, the place where his father lay decorated the mausoleum of Pahlavon Makhmud with tiles. This work he would send as early as may 1825 and be completed in the same year. Ollokulikhon's respect for his father was such that he ordered that the tomb he had prepared be built on the foot side of his father's Tomb. It is not difficult to notice that this tradition comes from the beginning, on the tip of the foot of Pahlavan Makhmud Abulghazi and Anushahans (tombstones of the 17th century), followed by the Tomb of Mukhammad Rakhimkhan I.

The koshin bricks on the inner walls of the shrine and Shrine of the mausoleum were chosen by one of the ruboyi of the Pahlavan Makhmud-Puryoyvali, and the four sides were beautifully inscribed on the wall in one line in a Nasta'liq letter. On the entrance door of the room where the grave of the paulvon father is located, this famous ruboie of him is inscribed:

¹⁰ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Olloqulixon>

¹¹ <https://khivamuseum.uz/uz/tosh-hovli-saroyi-xorazm-hunarmandchiligi-bolimi>

Uch yuz Ko'hi qofni kelida tuymoq,
Dil qonidan bermoq falakka bo'yoq.
Yoinki bir asr zindonda yotmoq,
Nodon suhbatidan ko'ra yaxshiroq.
(translation of To'xtasin Jalolov¹²).

Inscriptions on the mausoleum door.

The main entrance door of the mausoleum of Father polwon was installed in 1700 by Order of King Niyozhan, making the door an excellent example of the art of wood carving by master Nadr Mukhammad . A hadith is recited to his tawa: "the Prophet said:" Visit the people of qubur, if you are surprised by the parochial nature of your Affairs. "The reason why this hadith was written on the door of the mausoleum should be that when Ota Polvon went to India, he asked Khorazmshakh for permission to recite this hadith the day before the descent of the struggle with the Hindu Pahlavan and visited the cemeteries around him. It was this pilgrimage that chogi met the mother of an Indian polwon. After deliberately falling in the fight and giving the victory to the Indian polvoni, father Polvon noticed that his basirat eye was open. The feeling that came into his body through the defeat in this contest, the satisfaction that a strange feeling received from all the victories of his life, was superior to the pleasures. It was from this time that he learned that from his physical strength his spiritual strength was strong, that this power took over his entire body.

Another reason for this hadith to be ordered by King Niyazhan some four hundred years later and inscribed on this door may have been to bring it to the memory of the pilgrims. Because we know from his rubois that Paulvon wanted the father to do the same:

Kim qilur bu vayron dilim imorat?
Kim gunohim uchun berur kaforat?
Men ziyorat qildim ko'p qabristonni,
Bilmadim, kim qilur qabrim ziyorat?!

Translation of Muinzoda.

King Niyozkhan, who was considered extremely ambitious and expensive, was the Khan of Khiva in 1698-1703. King Niyozkhan had the entrance Gatehouse of Father Polwon's mausoleum built in his time, and also had a tomb prepared for himself in the same place.

Master Nadr Mukhammad , who decorated the doors of the gatehouse with beautiful patterns, also completed a poetic history for him. From this poetic

¹² https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/To%CA%BBxtasin_Jalolov

history it is revealed that King Niyozkhan repaired this luminous building, dug a well, and was himself buried in the same place. It is also a place where their heads are tied, and the healing of those who suffer from pain is a sign that the mausoleum is a center of healing:

Osmonga qarab o'q kabi otilgan,
Bu chiroyli gumbazning toqi.
Yo rab, boshlari bog'lanib dardga chalingan,
Xasta dillarning duolarini mustajob qil.
Adolatli Shoh Niyozxon himmati bilan,
Parvardigorning xohishlari amalga oshdi.
Bezakli bir bino va quduq bunyod qilib,
Buning bilan g'alaba eshigin din uchun ochdi.

King Niyozkhan died in 1703 and was buried at the site he had built west of the gatehouse.

The great ones buried in the mausoleum.

Mukhammad Rahimxon I. The tomb inside the ravine, built in a semi-circular shape on the grid of the mausoleum's great Khanakah, was buried by Mukhammad Rakhimkhan I, who ruled from 1806 to 1825. During his tenure, the country's territories were expanded, its position in Central Asia was strengthened, and ambassadorial ties were established with countries such as Turkey, Iran, Afghanistan, India Russia, Bukhara, Kokand. The Supreme Council was formed, which dealt with state issues related to domestic and foreign policy. Because Mukhammad Rakhimkhan spoke, read, and wrote in Arabic, Persian, and Turkic languages, the Awami people called him "Okhun Khan". Little sleep, a fan of the game of chess, respected the holidays, especially the holiday of the week benihoya. It was not based on the position or origin of a person, but on his work. "Mukhammad Rakhimkhan was tall, big-bodied, with a sharp gaze, strong-willed, brave and entrepreneurial, he could not be carried by a strong horse for more than two hours either." A man of great piety, who performed the pilgrimage of cemeteries everywhere.

Conclusion.

Based on the above information, we can state that Pakhlovon Makhmud was the beloved, patriotic child of his people. That is why the man who lived in the pain of the people is still revered to this day. It is known that the eternal living, eternal living, who lived with the pain of the people